

COMPARISON BETWEEN THE OUTCOMES OF TOTAL LAPAROSCOPIC HYSTERECTOMY AND TOTAL ABDOMINAL HYSTERECTOMY

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Introduction :

Hysterectomy is one of the most commonly performed gynecological procedures worldwide. It is indicated for a variety of benign and malignant conditions including uterine fibroids, abnormal uterine bleeding, adenomyosis, endometriosis, pelvic organ prolapse, and certain gynecologic cancers. Among benign indications, uterine fibroids and dysfunctional uterine bleeding remain the leading causes in reproductive-age women.

There are various surgical approaches to hysterectomy, including Total Abdominal Hysterectomy (TAH), Vaginal Hysterectomy (VH), Total Laparoscopic Hysterectomy (TLH), and Robotic-Assisted Laparoscopic Hysterectomy. Each technique has its own indications, benefits, and limitations depending on various factors such as uterine size, pelvic anatomy, Co morbidities, surgeon experience, and availability of resources.

TAH has traditionally been the most widely practiced method, particularly in low-resource settings, due to its technical familiarity and direct access to pelvic organs. Reich et al. reported first laparoscopic assisted vaginal hysterectomy case in 1989(1). Hence forth, minimally invasive approaches such as TLH have gained prominence owing to their association with reduced intra operative blood loss, shorter hospital stays, decreased postoperative pain, and quicker return to normal activities (2-5). Despite these advantages, the adoption of TLH has been limited in some regions due to the need for specialized training, longer operative times, and equipment costs.

Given the growing emphasis on minimally invasive surgery and patient-centered care, it is essential to evaluate and compare the outcomes of these surgical approaches. This study aims to compare TAH and TLH in terms of perioperative parameters, postoperative recovery, and complication rates in women undergoing hysterectomy for benign gynecologic conditions in Trichy SRM Medical College and Hospital situated in Tamil Nadu, India.

Materials and Methods:

Study Design and Settings:

This is a prospective, comparative observational study conducted over a period of 6 months from February 2025 – July 2025 at the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Trichy SRM Medical College and Hospital. The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee (Approval No. EC/NEW/INST/2024/4408; IEC No. 077) and informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Patient Selection:

A total of 100 women aged between 30 and 60 years, diagnosed with benign gynecological conditions requiring hysterectomy, were enrolled.

Inclusion criteria:

All patients with gynecological conditions necessitating Hysterectomy, of age between 30 and 60 years, regardless of BMI, previous abdomino-pelvic surgery and associated medical conditions of whom are undergoing TLH/TAH during February 2025 -July 2025 at Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research centre are to be taken into account.

Exclusion criteria:

Patient not giving consent for the study and Patients with apparent signs of malignancy in the pre operative evaluation is excluded from the study.

Study Groups

Patients were assigned into two groups based on the surgical technique employed:

- Group 1 (TAH): 50 patients who underwent total abdominal hysterectomy via a Suprapubic Transverse incision or midline incision under Regional Anaesthesia.
- Group 2 (TLH): 50 patients who underwent total laparoscopic hysterectomy performed using standard four-port technique under general anaesthesia.

Method:

Demographic details, anthropometry and detailed history including the chief complaints, duration, menstrual and obstetric history, past medical and surgical history were registered. Clinical examinations done and findings noted. Radiological findings were registered. Clinical diagnosis made out and patients were planned for Total abdominal hysterectomy or Total Laparoscopic Hysterectomy according to the clinical conditions. Patients were preoperatively evaluated thoroughly.

Both the groups received Pre- and Post-operative antibiotics.

All surgeries were performed by experienced gynecologic surgeons proficient in both techniques.

Operating time was calculated from the time of skin incision to the time of last suture.

Preoperative haemoglobin and Post operative first day haemoglobin was taken into account. And the need for blood transfusion was also taken into account.

Post operative adequate pain relief was given for both group of patients.

Intra operative and post operative complications were monitored. The complications were graded according to the Clavien-Dindo staging.

Conversion to laparotomy (in case of TLH), Length of hospital and time to achieve well being evaluated by a visual analog scale for global quality of life were also taken note off.

Patients were followed up postoperatively daily until they were at the hospital. They were then contacted over phone to check for any complications, and they came for review after a week. Patients were recommended to contact us if in case of presence of symptoms like fever, abdominal pain, vaginal bleeding, or any discomfort.

Groups are compared in terms of mean age, body mass index (BMI), operation time, blood loss, complication rate and postoperative hospitalization time.

Continuous variables are to be reported as mean and standard deviation. Categorical data are to be expressed as absolute number and percentage.. Data analysis was done with chi square and student-t tests of SPSS program. $p < 0.05$ value was regarded as statistically significant.

RESULTS :

DEMOGRAPHICS:

Age distribution:

The study included 100 participants (50 participants in each group) with a predominant age distribution in the 41–50 years category 60% (n=30) in Group 1 and 56% (n=28) in Group 2, followed closely by the 51–65 years category 22% (n=11) in Group 1 and 26% (n=16) in Group 2 while smaller proportions were noted among the 31–40 years 18% (n=9) in Group 1 and 12% (n=6) in Group 2. There is no Statistical significance in relation to age between both groups.

Table 1: Age Distribution of Study Participants

Age Category (in years)	TAH n=50 n (%)	TLH n=50 n (%)	p value
31-40	9 (18)	6 (12)	0.348
41-50	30 (60)	28 (56)	
51-65	11 (22)	13 (26)	
>65	0 (0)	3 (6)	

Body Mass Index:

Body mass index in both groups was similar and there is no statistical significance.

PRESENTING COMPLAINTS:

Heavy menstrual bleeding is the most common presenting symptom reported in 86% (n=43) in Group 1 and 84% (n=42) in Group 2, while post menopausal bleeding is noted in 4% (n=2) and 10% (n=5) in Group 1 and Group 2 patients respectively. Heavy Menstrual Bleeding with severe abdominal pain in 4% patients (n=2) of Group 1 and nil in Group 2.

Inter-menstrual bleeding is seen in 6% (n=3) of both groups.

Table 2: Distribution of Presenting Complaints in Study Participants

Chief Complaints	TAH n=50 n (%)	TLH n=50 n (%)	p value
HMB	43 (86)	42 (84)	0.421
PMB	2 (4)	5 (10)	
HMB with severe abdominal pain	2 (4)	0 (0)	
Inter-menstrual bleeding	3 (6)	3 (6)	
Mass descending P/V	0 (0)	0 (0)	

The mean duration of the disease in Group 1 is 7.94 ± 3.6 months. The mean duration of the disease in Group 2 is 6.22 ± 3.04 months.

UTERINE SIZE :

Uterine size is measured both radiologically and estimated clinically. According to clinical evaluation, 44% of patients (n=22) in Group 1 and 50% of patients (n=25) in Group 2 were found to have uterus of 12–14 weeks size. Normal sized uterus is seen in 30% patients (n=15) and 26% patients (n=13) in Group 1 and Group 2 respectively. 14% patients (n=7) have been found to have uterine size of 16-18 weeks in both Group 1 and Group 2. 4% patients (n=2) in Group 1 and 8% patients (n=4) in Group 2 are found to have 20-22 weeks size of uterus. Group 1 has 8% patients (n=4) and Group 2 has 2% patients (n=1) in the category of 24-26 weeks of uterine size.

Table 3: Distribution of Uterine Size among both Groups of Study Participants

Uterine Size	TAH n=50 n (%)	TLH n=50 n (%)	p value
12-14 weeks	22 (44)	25 (50)	0.639
16-18 weeks	7 (14)	7 (14)	
20-22 weeks	2 (4)	4 (8)	
24-26 weeks	4 (8)	1 (2)	

Normal size	15 (30)	13 (26)
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Figure 1 showing the Distribution of Uterine size among both Groups of Study Participants

CLINICAL DIAGNOSIS:

The most common clinical diagnosis was AUB – L accounting for 68% in Group 1 and 70% in Group 2 followed by AUB -A and AUB -E and 3rd Degree UV prolapse. Smaller proportion of patients also presented with complaints of AUB-M, AUB-O, AUB – L, P, AUB-A, O and CIN. Detailed distribution of the clinical diagnosis among the patients of both study group is presented in the table below. (Table 4).

Table 4: Distribution of Clinical diagnosis

Diagnosis	TAH n=50 n(%)	TLH n=50 n(%)
3rd degree UV Prolapse	3 (6)	4 (8)
AUB - A	5 (10)	5 (10)
AUB - A, O	1 (2)	0 (0)
AUB - E	3 (6)	4 (8)
AUB - L	34 (68)	35 (70)
AUB - L, P	1 (2)	0 (0)
AUB - M	1 (2)	0 (0)

AUB - O	1 (2)	0 (0)
CIN	1 (2)	2 (4)

Figure 2: Distribution of Clinical Diagnosis in TAH vs TLH

MEAN OPERATING TIME:

Mean operating time in Group 1 (TAH) is 121.96 +/- 2.1 mins.

Mean operating time in Group 2 (TLH) is 101.2 +/- 2.54 mins. P value is <0.001 and its is Stastically significant. The operating time is longer in Group 1 when compared to Group 2.

Table 5: Comparison of Operating Time between both Groups

Variables	TAH Mean ± S.D	TLH Mean ± S.D	p value
Operating Time (in mins)	121.96 ± 2.1 mins	101.2 ± 2.54 mins	<0.001

AMOUNT OF BLOOD LOSS:

Mean blood loss in Group 1 (TAH) is 517.5+/-2.2 ml.

Mean blood loss in Group 2 (TLH) is 211.5+/- 2.06 ml.

Mean blood loss is higher in patients who underwent total abdominal hysterectomy (Group 1) when compared to those who underwent total laparoscopic hysterectomy (Group 2) and it is statistically significant.

Table 6 : Comparison of Amount of Blood Loss between both Groups

Variables	TAH	TLH	p value
	Mean ± S.D	Mean ± S.D	
Amount of blood Loss (in ml)	517.5 ± 2.2	211.5 ± 2.06	<0.001

The blood loss is more in cases of larger uterine fibroids. The amount of blood is directly proportional to the size of the uterus in both the groups. It is statistically significant. But the need for blood transfusion doesn't correlate directly to the uterine size.

Table 4: Distribution of Uterine Size with Operating Time, Amount of Blood loss and Need for blood transfusion

Group	Variable	Operating Time (in mins)	Amount of Blood Loss (in ml)	Pre op Hb	Post op Hb	Need for Blood Transfusion
		Mean ± S.D	Mean ± S.D	Mean ± S.D	Mean ± S.D	n (%)
Uterine Size						
Group I	12-14 weeks	118.09±23.1	483.41±174.57	11.28±0.89	10.2±1.07	3(13.64%)
	16-18 weeks	118.57±24.78	527.14±185.27	11±0.68	10.07±1.1	1 (14.29%)
	20-22 weeks	155±7.07	875±176.78	11.4±0.57	8±0	2(100%)
	24-26 weeks	147.5±27.54	762.5±359.11	10.38±0.48	8.23±1.27	2(50%)
	Normal size	118±22.98	450±202.66	11.11±0.97	10.33±1.23	1(6.67%)
	p value	0.057	0.012	0.406	0.004	
	12-14 weeks	98.8±19.27	198.6±59.43	10.66±0.47	10.22±0.5	0

Group II	16-18 weeks	108.57±26.1	240.71±165.89	10.76±0.6	9.87±1.03	1(14.29%)
	20-22 weeks	117.5±23.63	343.75±290.38	10.68±0.79	33.58±48.96	1(25%)
	24-26 weeks	160±0	500±0	10±0	8.7±0	1(100%)
	Normal size	92.31±12.85	157.69±34.5	10.64±0.45	10.15±0.41	0
	p value	0.006	0.005	0.746	0.022	

18% of patients in Group 1 (TAH) received blood transfusion postoperatively. 6% of patients in Group 2 (TLH) received blood transfusion postoperatively. The chance of blood transfusion is higher in patients who underwent Total Abdominal Hysterectomy. It is statistically significant.

INTRAOPERATIVE AND POST OPERATIVE COMPLICATIONS :

Table 5: Distribution of Uterine Size with complications and blood transfusion

Group	Variables	12-14 weeks (n=47) n (%)	16-18 weeks (n=14) n (%)	20-22 weeks (n=6) n (%)	24-26 weeks (n=5) n (%)	Normal size (n=28) n (%)
Group I	Bleeding					
	Yes	4 (18.18)	2 (28.57)	2 (100)	2 (50)	2 (13.33)
	No	18 (81.82)	5 (71.43)	0 (0)	2 (50)	13 (86.67)
	Bladder Injury					
	Yes	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
	No	22 (100)	7 (100)	2 (100)	4 (100)	15 (100)
	Ureteric Injury					
	Yes	1 (4.55)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (25)	0 (0)
	No	21 (95.45)	7 (100)	2 (100)	3 (75)	15 (100)
	Bowel Injury					
	Yes	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (6.67)
	No	22 (100)	7 (100)	2 (100)	4 (100)	14 (93.33)
	Fever					
	Yes	5 (22.73)	1 (14.29)	2 (100)	1 (25)	1 (6.67)
	No	17 (77.27)	6 (85.71)	0 (0)	3 (75)	14 (93.33)

	Wound Complications					
	Yes	3 (13.64)	0 (0)	0 (0)	2 (50)	0 (0)
	No	19 (86.36)	7 (100)	2 (100)	2 (50)	15 (100)
	Conversion to Open Laparotomy					
	Not Applicable	22 (100)	7 (100)	2 (100)	4 (100)	15 (100)
Group II	Bleeding					
	Yes	1 (4)	1 (14.29)	1 (25)	1 (100)	0 (0)
	No	24 (96)	6 (85.71)	3 (75)	0 (0)	13 (100)
	Bladder Injury					
	Yes	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
	No	25 (100)	7 (100)	4 (100)	1 (100)	13 (100)
	Ureteric Injury					
	Yes	0 (0)	1 (14.29)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
	No	25 (100)	6 (85.71)	4 (100)	1 (100)	13 (100)
	Bowel Injury					
	Yes	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
	No	25 (100)	7 (100)	4 (100)	1 (100)	13 (100)
	Fever					
	Yes	1 (4)	1 (14.29)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
	No	24 (96)	6 (85.71)	4 (100)	1 (100)	13 (100)
	Wound Complications					
	Yes	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
	No	25 (100)	7 (100)	4 (100)	1 (100)	13 (100)
	Conversion to Open Laparotomy					
	No	25 (100)	7 (100)	3 (75)	1 (100)	13 (100)
	Yes	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (25)	0 (0)	0 (0)

From the above-mentioned table (Table 5) it is clear that bleeding is more encountered in cases undergoing TAH when compared to TLH. Bladder injury is not seen in both groups. Ureteric injury is common in Group 1 when compared to Group 2. Bowel injury is seen in one patient of Group 1. No bowel injury encountered in Group 2. Wound complications are more common with group 1 and no wound complications noted in group 2. Conversion to Open laparotomy occurred in one patient of Group 2.

LENGTH OF HOSPITAL STAY:

The mean length of hospital stay in group 1 and group 2 is respectively 7.04+/- 1.3 days and 3.26 +/- 1.96 days respectively.

Table 6: Comparison of Clinical Outcomes Between TAH and TLH Groups

Variables	TAH Mean ± S.D	TLH Mean ± S.D	p value
Operating Time (in mins)	121.96 ± 2.1 mins	101.2 ± 2.54 mins	<0.001
Amount of blood Loss (in ml)	517.5 ± 2.2 ml	211.5 ± 2.06 ml	<0.001
Length of Hospital Stay (in days)	7.04 ± 1.3 days	3.26 ± 1.96 days	<0.001

DISCUSSION:

The findings of this study align with global evidence favoring TLH over TAH in terms of recovery, pain, blood loss, shorter hospital stay, cosmetic reasons and faster time to achieve well being. This is consistent with studies by Nieboer et al. and Aarts et al. The age and BMI were similar among both groups and there was no statistical significance. By our study, The Mean operating time was higher in patients who underwent TAH in comparison with TLH. This was not in accordance with study conducted by Olsson et al. and Härkki-Sirén et al. and Çelik et al., who reported correspondingly that operation time for TLH is statistically significant longer than TAH (5-7).

By our study the mean blood loss is more in TAH when compared to TLH. In a lot of studies intraoperative and perioperative blood loss in laparoscopic hysterectomy was less than abdominal hysterectomy (8,9,10). Raju and Auld, Çelik et al., Seracchioli et al. and Ribeiro et al. found out no statistically significant difference about blood loss between TLH and TAH (11,12).

Garry et al. reported in their eVALuate trial, in which 1380 women included, laparoscopic hysterectomy is related with more complications than abdominal hysterectomy (13). But in our study more complications are noted with total abdominal hysterectomy.

Overall, laparoscopic hysterectomy is a well-tolerated and beneficial technique in suitable candidates, leading to lower complication rates, shorter hospital stays, and enhanced postoperative quality of life.

REFERENCES:

1. Reich H. New techniques in advanced laparoscopic surgery. *Baillieres Clin Obstet Gynaecol* 1989; 3:655-81.
2. Liu CY. Laparoscopic hysterectomy. Report of 215 cases. *Gynecol Endosc* 1992; 1:73-7.
3. Phipps JP, John M, Nayak S. Comparison of laparoscopic assisted vaginal hysterectomy and bilateral salpingo-ophorectomy with conventional abdominal hysterectomy and bilateral salpingo-ophorectomy. *Br J Obstet Gynaecol* 1993; 110:698-700.
4. Raju KS, Auld BJ. A randomized prospective study of laparoscopic vaginal hysterectomy versus abdominal hysterectomy each with bilateral salpingoophorectomy. *Br J Obstet Gynaecol* 1994; 101:1068-71.
5. Olsson JH, Ellström M, Hahlin M. A randomized prospective trial comparing laparoscopic and abdominal hysterectomy. *Br J Obstet Gynaecol* 1996; 103:345-50.
6. Härkki-Sirén P, Sjöberg J, Toivonen J, Tiitinen A. Clinical outcome and tissue trauma after laparoscopic and abdominal hysterectomy: a randomized controlled study. *Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand* 2000; 79:866-71.
7. Çelik C, Abali R, Tasdemir N, Aksu E, Çalışkan H, Akkuş D. Total Laparoskopik Histerektomi ve Abdominal Histerektomi Karşılaştırılması; Klinik Sonuçlar. *JCAM* 2014 Published online. DOI: 10.4328/JCAM.1513.
8. Howard FM, Sanchez R. A comparison of laparoscopic assisted vaginal hysterectomy and abdominal hysterectomy. *J Gynecol Surg* 1993; 9:83-90.
9. Nezhat F, Nezhat C, Gordons S, Wilkins F. Laparoscopic versus abdominal hysterectomy. *J Reprod Med* 1992; 37:247-50.
10. Perino A, Cucinella G, Venezia R, Castelli A, Cittadini E. Total laparoscopic hysterectomy versus total abdominal hysterectomy: an assessment of the learning curve in a prospective randomized study. *Hum Reprod* 1999; 14:2996-9.
11. Çelik C, Abali R, Tasdemir N, Aksu E, Çalışkan H, Akkuş D. Total Laparoskopik Histerektomi ve Abdominal Histerektomi Karşılaştırılması; Klinik Sonuçlar. *JCAM* 2014 Published online. DOI: 10.4328/JCAM.1513.
12. Seracchioli R, Venturoli S, Vianello F, Govoni F, Cantarelli M, Gualerzi B, et al. Total laparoscopic hysterectomy compared with abdominal hysterectomy in the presence of a large uterus. *J Am Ass Gynecol Laparosc* 2002; 9:333-8.
13. Garry R, Fountain J, Mason S, Hawe J, Napp V, Abbott J, Clayton R, Phillips G, Whittaker M, Lilford R, Bridgman S, Brown J. The eVALuate study: two parallel randomised trials, one comparing laparoscopic with abdominal hysterectomy, the other comparing laparoscopic with vaginal hysterectomy. *BMJ* 2004; 328:129.